

Semantics of *-i-*, *-ith-* Causative Morphemes in Gichuka

Nelly Karimi Mbaka ✉

*Department of Languages, School of Education and Social Sciences,
Karatina University, Kenya*

Abstract

Knowledge of a language entails an understanding of the components and levels of its grammar, and how these levels interact to bring about holistic grammars. It is, therefore, prudent that linguists describe each level in order to shed light into the inter-componential relationships in languages. This in turn reveals how each level and component contributes to creation of a language's lexicon. This paper investigated the morpho-semantic component of Gichuka Language, specifically, the meanings deciphered with the use of morphemes *-i-* and *-ith-* regarded causatives. The aim was to unravel the semantics conveyed when licensed by *-i-ith-*. This work sought to address questions surrounding the semantics *-i-* and *-ith-* causatives licence, the productivity of the readings and how components of grammar interact to bring forth *-i-ith-*. Here, we note that the suffixes are constituted in the morphological domain whereas the readings are in semantics. Findings point out at an existence of an inter-componential relationship, specifically, adjectives are labialized with /b/ triggered by *-i-* (about 95%) (morpho-phonology), the two morphemes are suffixes creating complexes (morphology) and that they convey different readings besides causation (semantics). Further, varying semantics were noted in the order of productivity as; coercion, trickery, adversative, assistance, accidental and idiomatization. Coercion is licenced by inappropriately used instruments, instruments with defects and forced causes, assistance is associated with help while trickery is conveyed when *-ith-* licences an action through cunningness. In adversity, it is the causer and not the causee that is affected negatively. The idiomatic reading is conveyed when the meaning is deciphered and unrelated to the morpho-phonological *-i-*, *-ith-* all together.

Keywords: *Causation, Coercion, labialization, Reading, Licence.*

Suggested citation: Mbaka, N.K. (2024). Semantics of *-i-*, *-ith-* Causative Morphemes in Gichuka. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 1(3), 145-160. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2024.1(3).09

Introduction

Bantu languages highly agglutinative and as such, they have highly productive verbal suffixes that alter semantics and valences of verb roots (Good, 2005). Such is the causative suffix marking causation, a process that makes one event to produce another. It is a form attached to the verb to indicate that the subject causes someone or something else to do something or cause a change of state of a non-volitional event. There are many ways in which causation can be realized, among them lexical, analytic and morphological. Although, scholars such as (Muriungi, 2010) and Mbaka & Kirigia (2023) have laid a lot of emphasis on the morphological causation, which involves causative morphemes, little has been done with this regard to Gichuka and the vast semantics causatives can convey. A keen scrutiny of causatives in Gichuka points out that, once a morphological causation is applied; a variety of semantics may be realized. Besides, there are

notable effects of the morphology on phonology. This proves linguists claim of inter-componential relationships within language grammars, which is well illustrated in Distributed Morphology (DM) by Halle and Marantz (1993). DM highlights the fact that morphology is not concentrated in a single component of grammar but is distributed among several other components, a notion also shared by Baker (1988) in his Mirror Principle, which states that “morphological operations reflect (mirror) syntactic operations.”

From the production, manipulations, and mechanisms such as move, merge and application of rules to realization as vocabulary item for insertion at spell-out stage, different levels interplay. This paper has attempted to document this interplay among at least three levels; morphology, morpho-phonology and semantics. Furthermore, facts about how the causative morphemes behave, either independently or in the company of each other have not been established. Linguists are, therefore, faced with the temptation of treating them as a bi-partite, a morpheme made up of two parts while in actual sense there is evidence that each is an independent morpheme. This paper establishes that the two may occur independently or co-occur and when used, a variety of interpretations are realized. Depending on the context of insertion and usage, the varying readings conveyed can be ranked in the order of productivity with the most productive (coercion) ranking highest and the least (idiomatization) ranking lowest.

Although largely known for causation, the reading of idiomatization with -i- neither denotes nor connotes any semantics near causation. In this discovery, the ‘causative -i-’ may also be regarded as an ‘*idiomatizing*’ morpheme.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Chuka Division, Tharaka Nithi County-Kenya. This is an area concentrated with Gichuka speaking population, being near Chuka Town, the Head Quarters of The County at the time of this study. The study employed descriptive design according to which, McCombes (2019) asserts that a phenomenon, a population or a situation is systematically and accurately described as it is. In this study, the researcher analyzed and described the participants’ responses as they were presented through the SGTs and focus group interactions. This entailed a detailed description and reporting of the nature of two extensions, how they differ or are similar in Gichuka, whether or not they co-occur and to what extent. This is what Kombo and Tromp (2006) refer to as ‘state of affairs as is.’

Data generalized over a target population of about one hundred thousand Gichuka speakers according to Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, National Population and Housing Census Report conducted in 2019 (KNBS, 2020). A sample size of ten adult participants was preferred as motivated by Gentel et al. (2015), who posit that a small sample is appropriate for a descriptive study that focuses on acquiring information that is helpful in understanding the complexity, depth, variation or context surrounding a given phenomenon..

The respondents were sampled based on the criteria of age, level of education and language proficiency, both in English and local language. Concerning age, adult speakers of between 40 and 55 years were considered. The justification for this age bracket is that the speakers are unlikely affected by the neighboring linguistic environments as would be the younger ones. Speakers of this age have also been found to describe abstract information better based on their social experiences (White, 2001). In a majority of cases, the respondents within this age can visualize the intent of a research, owing to their optimal stage, 55 years is the age considered by the government as the active margin, beyond which is considered fatigued and not fair for subjection to what would be considered language games of such nature as morphology.

Level of education as another criterion employed in this study was considered on the basis that individuals of different educational levels view issues differently. People's level of education has been seen to influence their ability to form opinions and synthesis of abstract information (Carlson et al., 2015). An educated respondent is likely to form better attitudes, understand better the importance of a study and appreciate scholarship than their uneducated counterpart, moreover, there is a tendency of people at lower educational levels to undermine themselves in a research process, especially when the researcher is one among them. To this end, all the ten participants had attained a post primary level.

Language proficiency in both English and the local language was the third criterion for selection of participants of this research. There were two justifications for this; one for English and the other for the local language. Proficiency in English was justified by the inadequacy of vocabulary in Gichuka for defining individual morphemes. The explanation for the application of the many morphemes there are in the language was not a matter of plug and play, it was, therefore, found prudent to include some of the instructions in SGTs and FGDs in English in order for them to grasp a rough idea of what was required upon explanation.

A competent speaker of a language can handle any idea, abstract or concrete in their language with more ease than a learner at whichever age. Mastery and competence was checked alongside Chomsky's competence theory (Chomsky, 1988). He notes that when one claims to know a language, they have grammatical and pragmatic competences. Grammatical competence entails the three linguistic abilities found in any language namely: phonological, syntactic and semantic. The recognition of sounds in a language (phonology) enables one to string them together into words and words in certain ways to form sentences (syntax), and to recognize well-formed from ill-formed structures, in as far as sound sequences and meanings (semantics) are concerned. Pragmatic competence on the other hand, addresses the role played by the extra-linguistic information like attitude, personal biases and opinions in the interpretation of sentences. Pragmatic competence was found to play a great role in interpretation of non-verbal data in this study, especially in focus groups. It was believed, therefore, that an adult native Gichuka speaker who has attained these levels of competences can guarantee authentic responses as a linguistic research respondent.

Purposive sampling was considered in the selection of both the participants and the items in the tools. This allowed the researcher select cases with the desired characteristics according to Mugenda & Mugenda (1999). This was based on the propensity to elicit target structures as specified in the SGTs and FGDs. A blend of SGTs and FGDs as tools of data elicitation, a combination that provided cross-data validity checks, thereby reducing errors that can be experienced when one method is used in a study (Patton, 1990). The SGTs comprised structures with plain verbs in Gichuka. Verbs were broadly categorized into four classes namely: intransitive, transitive, lexical and adjectival. This is the broadest classification in which other sub-categories can be captured. From the four categories, five individual verbs were picked purposively from each, making a total of twenty items. The rationale for including the adjectives as a verbal category is the observation that upon subjection to extensions, they exhibit characteristics similar to those of verbs. Selection of individual verbs was based on Swadesh (1955), who provides a list of conventional words in languages. According to Swadesh, all or at least 98% of the world languages of whichever typology will contain that item. The sentences contained clear instructions on how to apply the varying verbal extensions.

Upon obtaining permit from the research authorizing body of Kenya, National Council of Science and Technology (NACOSTI) in order to conduct research, the respondents were clustered into two groups. Each cluster met at a time in order to spell out the intent and the kind of task ahead. Firstly were semi-formal, considered planning meetings.

The SGTs were administered to the respondents, who were already acquainted to them. They then filled in amid light consultations amongst themselves. The data on the SGTs were read, interpreted and translated into English for easier identification of extensions and semantics. Translation and interpretation was done systematically as it appeared in the SGTs, from transitives, intransitives, adjectivals and lexicals. Data from the focus groups were replayed and transcribed, then interpreted into English. Each set of data was categorized and coded depending on the tool of emanation. The two tools of data elicitation; SGT and FGD were labeled as T₁ and T₂ respectively. Thus; data from focus groups were coded T₂, while that from structures was coded T₁. Coding helped in easier identification of related data and was found invaluable in avoiding mix up and jumbled up analysis.

The responses were then analyzed and presented in words, phrases, clauses and sentences. Analysis was guided by glossing, usually referred to as Leipzig Glossing Rule adapted from Christian (1982) in its three levels of string representation. Consider exemplification at (1) for illustration of LGR. Level (i) is word, (ii) literal translation and (iii) free translation in English.

- (1) (i) *Mugendi a-ku-ring-ith-an-ang-ir-i-a nturume mu-gunda-ni*
(ii) Mugendi sa-tns-hit-caus-rec-err-appl-ic-fv rams 3shamba-loc
(iii) Mugendi has caused the rams to hit each other repeatedly in the field

The respondents were truthfully informed that data were solely for academic purposes and in particular for the current research. All participants were requested for consent in line with McNabb's (2004) provision that the principle of voluntary participation is central in any research. Further, they were made aware of their right to pull out from the process if one felt the need. The participants were promised confidentiality and anonymity, hence personal details were not required. No data were recorded without the respondents' knowledge. To avoid plagiarism, any work of other scholars or people cited has been appropriately acknowledged and included in the bibliography.

Results

Preliminary results show that Gichuka has two causative morphemes, -ith- and -i-, a trend adopted from the Proto-Bantu. This is because Bantu languages are highly conservative. The two are suffixes creating complexes (morphology) and that they convey different readings besides causation (semantics). Further, varying semantics were noted in the order of productivity as; coercion, trickery, adversative, assistance, accidental and idiomatization. Coercion is licenced by inappropriately used instruments, instruments with defects and forced causes, assistance is associated with help while trickery is conveyed when -ith- licences an action through cunningness. In adversity, it is the causer and not the causee that is affected negatively. The idiomatic reading is conveyed when the meaning is deciphered and unrelated to the morpho-phonological -i-, -ith- all together. Table 1 is an adaptation of Muringi 2010 and summarizes the causative contexts.

Table 1. Properties of Causative Contexts

	Direct causation	Indirect causation	Event may/ not result
Inappropriate Instrument	√	√	√
Defective Instruments	√	√	√
Forced Causes	√	√	√
Tricked Causes	√	√	√
Assistive	√	*	*

Adversative	√	*	*
Accidental	*	√	*
Idiomatic	-	-	-

Discussion

To create a causative expression in Gichuka, the morpheme *-ith-* or *-i-* is attached to the main verb. Both the causing and the caused events are encoded in a single verbal complex via a causative morpheme and a morphological marking on the verb showing the nature of the affected arguments. The two morphemes could occur separately or co-occur. In the presentation of data, sentences stated in Gichuka are first glossed word by word and then their English equivalents stated. This is the pattern used in linguistics to enable linguists who are not native speakers of the language understand the data easily.

-i- Causation

Consider the sentences below with the intransitive verbs *thek-a* (laugh) (2) and *nyar-a* (dry) (3)

- (2a) Mwana a-ku-thek-a
 Child sa-tns-laugh-fv
 ‘The child has laughed’

(2a) contains no causer and the event (laughing) is spontaneous. When *-i-* is added, the introduction of an external causer subject is obligatory as illustrated in (2b).

- (b) Kanana a-ku-thek-*i-a* mwana
 Kanana sa-tns- laugh -*caus*-fv mwana
 ‘Kanana has made the child laugh’

The verbal complex “a-ku-thek-*i-a*” contains the causer subject represented by the subject agreement (*sa*), the caused event (laugh) and the morphological causative marking *-i-*. Consider the verb *nyar* (dry) which can take both agentive and natural cause subjects.

- (3a) Nku i-ku- nyar -a
 Firewood-sa-tns-dry-fv
 ‘The firewood has dried’

When the causative morpheme *-i-* is introduced, the introduction of the causer is necessary, and this causer can either be agentive as in (3b) or a natural cause as in (3c)

- (b) Makena a-ku- nyar -*i-a* nku
 Makena sa-tns- dry -*caus*-fv-firewood
 ‘Makena has dried firewood’
- (c) Riua ri-ku- nyar -*i-a* nku
 Sun’s heat-sa-tns- dry -*cause*-fv- firewood
 ‘The sun’s heat has dried the firewood.’

From the examples (2b, 3b and 3c), the following observations can be made about -i- causation; (i) An external subject called causer is added. This is why there is Kanana (2b), Makena (3b) and riuua (3c) which were not there in (2a) and (3a) respectively.

(ii) Both verbs thek-a (laugh) and nyar-a (dry) are intransitive but on causation, they take the objects mwana (child) and nku (firewood) respectively.

(iii) The NPs (mwana) in (2a) and (nku) in (3a) were subjects before causation but become objects after causation. It is therefore, appropriate to say that besides being a causative, -i- is also a transitivizer, making intransitive verbs take objects.

-ith- Causation

The behavior of -ith- causative is not different from that of its counterpart -i- in that both of them introduce a causer subject, transitivize intransitives and di-transitivize transitives. Consider example

(4).

(4a) Gatwiri a-ku- ob -a- nku
Gatwiri -sa-tns tie -fv- firewood
'Gatwiri has tied firewood'

(b) Kanana a-ku- ob -ith-i-a Gatwiri nku
Kanana -sa-tns- tie -caus-ic-fv- Gatwiri firewood
'Kanana has caused Gatwiri to tie firewood'

There are four properties notable about morphological causation in Gichuka so far;

- (i) -ith and -i- are bound morphemes which cannot stand on their own but rely on the main verb for causative semantics.
- (ii) Both are cases of suffixation
- (iii) Together with the main verb, they form a single verbal complex, which can function as a verb group on its own.
- (iv) While -i- is strictly an internal causer, -ith- is both an internal and synthetic causer. In internal causation, the introduced causer is also the agent of causation, whereas, in synthetic causation, the introduced causer is different since the initial subject becomes the agent of causation. A stronger tendency noted is for -i- to attach on intransitives and -ith- to transitives. This does not disregard the fact that a few intransitive verbs use -ith- for causation. Verbs like nyar (dry) and gw-a (fall) which are agentive intransitives may use -ith- for causation (gwithia and nyarithia). In both, however, there is the reading of causation. What is of interest in this paper is the contexts of and the differences in interpretations of causation in these contexts.

Semantics of the Causative Morpheme(s)

The semantics of the causative morpheme refer to the interpretations conveyed when the causative morpheme *-ith-* or *-i-* embeds a subject to bring about a causative event. The embedded subject can be animate or inanimate, and depending on the nature of the subject, the event may or not. The following are the interpretations of the causative constructions in Gichuka.

(a) Coercion

This is the interpretation derived when the causative morpheme *-ith-* is licensed by embedded arguments that are either defectively used instruments, inappropriately used instruments or forced causees.

(i) Use of Defective Instruments

The instrument is interpreted as having been coerced (forced) into doing something (event) despite its defects. This could be a machine, for instance, which should be doing some specific job but because of the faults (defects), it cannot do so. When it is used with *-ith-*, the interpretation is that of coercion. Take for instance a chaff cutter that is not faulty as in (5a).

- (5a) Kithii gi-ku-thi-a- ria
Chaff-cutter -sa-tns- grind -fv- chaff
'The chaff-cutter has shredded chaff.'

(5a) is a statement to the effect that the machine (chaff-cutter) shredded the chaff. With the introduction of *-ith-*, the chaff-cutter is interpreted as having been coerced in that, although it is supposed to shred chaff, it had some defects at that particular time, hence it is being coerced. Consider (b)

- (b) Mbungu a-ku- thi -**ith-i-a-** kithii ria
Mbungu -sa-tns- grind -**crv-ic-**fv- chaff-cutter chaff.
'Mbungu has **coerced** the chaff-cutter into shredding chaff.'

If this is a chaff-cutting machine, it need not be subjected to *-ith-* (force) and the causer introduced as this is what it should be doing. Otherwise, the defect is intuitively felt although it could overtly be indicated by the phrase "gi kithuku" (spoil). Maybe the blade had broken as in (c).

- (c) Mbungu -a-ku- thi -**ith-i-a-** kithii -gi-ki- thuku ria
Mbungu -sa-tns- grind -**crv-ic-**fv- chaff-cutter- chaff when -sa- spoil
'Mbungu forced the chaff-cutter into shredding chaff when spoilt.'

In the context of defective instruments, the event may or may not occur depending on the extent of the defect. For instance, the chaff-cutter may shred the chaff because of the friction on its working surfaces from the applied pressure, or it may also not in that though there is friction and pressure, the remaining part of the blade could be too blunt or weak to obtain the event as in (6).

- (6) Mbungu a-ku- thi -**ith-i-a-** kithii ria indi gi-ta-thi-a-
Mbungu-sa-tns- grind -**crv-ic-**fv- chaff-cutter but -sa-neg- grind -fv
'Mbungu forced the chaff-cutter into shredding chaff but it did not.'

(ii) Inappropriately used instruments

When a subject is embedded by *-ith-*, a possible interpretation is that the instrument has been used inappropriately. Take for instance a sewing needle subjected to stitching leather. Consider (7a) which is a neutral statement to the effect that the needle sewed clothes.

- (7a) cindano -ni-i-a- tum -ir-e- nguo
 needle -f-sa-tns-sew -pfv -fv- clothes
 ‘The needle sewed clothes.’

When the external causer is introduced and the needle embedded by *-ith-* the interpretation is that the needle is used inappropriately as in (b)

- (b) Wanja -a-gu- tum **-ith-i-a-** cindano nguo
 Wanja -sa-tns- sew **-crv-ic-fv-** needle clothes
 ‘Wanja has coerced the needle into sewing clothes.’

The inappropriateness of the instrument could be overtly stated by use of a prepositional phrase stating the specialized purpose for the instrument, for instance stitching leather in our case as (8).

- (8) Mukami -a-gu- tum **-ith-i-a-** cindano (ya iratu) nguo
 Mukami -sa-tns cut **-crv-ic-fv-** (for shoes) clothes
 ‘Mukami has used an awl for sewing clothes.’

The inappropriate use of the needle has been overtly indicated by the use of the prepositional phrase “for shoes” (ya iratu). Maybe it is extremely thick, blunt and very rough such that on piercing clothes, it would just damage the material. After all, the coercive context with inappropriately used instruments could be taken to be a result of using the instruments against their intended function. As with defectively used instruments, when an inappropriate instrument is coerced, the event may result or fail. The defective and inappropriate instruments should be understood as inanimate man-made objects such that inanimate natural objects like a log cannot license *-ith-*. It is wrong to say for instance that a log was coerced into destroying a house as shown in (9);

- (9) *Kagwiria -ni-a-omor **-ith-ir-i-e-** nkungugu nyomba
 Maria -f-sa- destroy **-crc-pfv-ic-fv-** log house
 ‘Maria coerced the log into destroying the house.’

(iii) Forced causees

Consider the neutral sentence (10a) to the effect that the witch took the oath.

(10a) Murogi a-ku- nyu -a- muuma
Witch -sa-tns- drink fv- oath
'The witch has taken the oath.'

Embedded by *-ith-* in (b), the interpretation is that the witch could not casually take the oath, considering the implications of the action. He must have been forced either directly (whipped) or indirectly (threatened).

(b) Akuru -ma-ku- nyu **-ith-i-a-** murogi muuma
Elders -sa-tns- drink **-crv-ic-**fv- witch oath

The correct interpretation could either be (i) or (ii) and not (iii)

- (i) The elders whipped the witch and he took the oath.
- (ii) The elders threatened to burn the witch and he took the oath.
- (iii) *The elders just asked the witch to take the oath and he did.

In this context, the embedded subject is animate and the occurrence of the event solely depends on the circumstances or the nature of the causee; it may or may not hold. For instance the witch was very stubborn and declined completely to take the oath, especially if he had committed the crime for which the oath is being administered and he understands the repercussions. This is illustrated in (11).

(11) Akuru ma-ku- nyu **-ith-i-a-** murogi muuma indi -a-ta-nyu-a
Elders -sa-tns- drink **-crv-ic-**fv- witch oath but -sa-neg- drink -fv
'The elders coerced the witch into taking the oath but he did not.'

(b) Assistive

The assistive reading of the causative morpheme has two varieties. In one, physical contact during assistance is involved, for instance helping a baby get on the bed as in (12b)

(12a) Mwana a-gu-tw-a- gitandani
Child -sa-tns- climb -fv- bed
'The child has climbed the bed.'

- (b) Mwiti a-gu-tw-**ith-i-a**- mwana gitandani
 Mwiti -sa-tns- climb -**crv-ic**-fv- child bed
 ‘Mwiti has helped the child to climb the bed.’

In (b) the interpretation is that the child was assisted to get on the bed; may be the bed was high and Mwiti lifted the baby and placed it on the bed as she is a small child. The other variety involves motion verbs like *ngaria* (run) and *thiuba* (walk fast) among others, the causer must be beside the causee during the time of the aid in movement and the location is obligatory. Consider example (13) below;

- (13) Kawiria -a-ku- ngar -**ith-i-a**-Maua cukuru
 Kawiria sa-tns- run -**crv-ic**-fv- Maua school
 ‘Kawiria has helped Maua run to school.’
 (She ran besides her, probably holding her hand, Maua may be a small girl).

Assistive interpretation is a case of direct causation. For instance, in physical assistance, physical contact between the causer and the causee is mandatory. The causer and the causee must be beside each other during the time of movement and the event must always obtain. It is therefore, infelicitous to say that Mwiti assisted the child to get on the bed but the child did not, as shown in (14).

- (14) * Mwiti -a-gu- tw -**ith-i-a**- mwana gitandani indi -a-ta-tw-a
 Mwiti -sa-tns- climb -**crv-ic**-fv- child bed but -sa-neg-climb fv
 ‘Mwiti assisted the child to climb the bed but the child did not’

(c) Trickery

A sentence with a tricked causee can also license **-ith-**. Consider example (15a) which is a neutral statement to mean that Muthoni bathed.

- (15a) Muthoni ni-a-a- thamb -ir-e- mwiri
 Muthoni -f-sa- tns- wash -pfv-fv- body
 ‘Muthoni bathed.’

Muthoni does not like bathing but her sister can trick her into bathing by lying to her that they are going to town as shown in (b).

- (b) Gatwiri -ni-a-a- thamb -**ith-ir-i-e** Muthoni mwiri
 Gatwiri -f-sa-tns wash -**crv-pfv-ic**-fv- Muthoni body

‘Gatwiri tricked Muthoni that they were going to town and she bathed.’

The example in (b) cannot mean that Gatwiri asked Muthoni to bathe and she did. The inference is that Muthoni was tricked. The interpretation is that Gatwiri tricked Muthoni (that they were going to town) so she bathed. The event with tricked causees does not have to result. For instance, Muthoni does not like bathing at all and no amount of cajoling or tricking may get her into bathing. She may even forfeit going to town as in (16).

- (16) Gatwiri -a-ku-thamb **-ith-i-a-** Mukami mwiri indi -a-ta-thamb -a-
Gatwiri -sa-tns- bathe **-caus-ic-fv-** Mukami body but -sa-neg- bathe
‘Gatwiri tricked Muthoni to bathe but she did not.’

Whenever there is trickery reading when **-ith-** embeds a causee, coercive reading is also present. For instance (16) could be interpreted as Gatwiri forcing Muthoni to bathe.

(d) Adversative

In adversative semantics, the embedded subject is affected negatively. Consider example (17a) which is a neutral sentence, to mean the Sunday school won the music competitions.

- (17a) Candi-i-gu- cind -a- nyimbo
Sunday school -sa-tns- win -fv- song
‘The Sunday school has won the music competitions.’

When **-ith-** is added as in (b) the meaning conveyed is that Gaceri made the Sunday school lose the music competitions and not Gaceri made the school win the music competitions. The results are negative and affect the embedded subject.

- (b) Gaceri -a-gu- cind **-ith-i-a-** candi nyimbo
Gaceri -sa-tns- win **-crv-ic-fv-** Sunday school song
‘Gaceri has made the Sunday school lose the music competition.’

The embedded subject ‘candi’ is affected negatively. If one wants to mean that Gaceri made the Sunday school win the music competition, the analytic causative ‘TUM-A’ (no details) is used as shown in (18)

- (18) Gaceri -a-gu- **tum-a-** candi -ya- cind-a- nyimbo
Gaceri -sa-tns- make -fv- Sunday school -sa- win -fv- song
‘Gaceri has made the Sunday school to win in the music competition.’

According to Muriungi (2010), a defining property of adversative reading of the causative in Kiitharaka is that the complement of **-ith-** sounds like a concealed passive with the reading X

caused Y to be v-ed by Z and not the expected X caused Y to v Z. Although in causation the first object after the verbal complex is usually the agent argument, in adversative reading it is the patient. Most Gichuka experiencer verbs such as rum-a/kab-a (bite), ring-a (hit) and cind-a (win) among others show this reading. Consider (19) bite for rum-a (19)

- (19) Gaceri a-ku- rum **-ith-i-a-** mwana kuru
 Gaceri -sa-tns- bite **-crv-ic-fv-** child dog
 ‘Gaceri made the child to be bitten by the dog.’

The semantics conveyed is that Gaceri caused the child to be bitten by a dog. It could be that Gaceri provoked a dog that was near a child and it bit it (child). Adversative reading can be achieved through direct causation and the event must hold. It is, therefore, not correct to say that *Gaceri made the school to lose the competition but it did not.*

(e) Accidental Reading

Consider sentence (20).

- (20) Mwana -a-gu- tink **-ith-i-a-** ng’ina gitinko
 Child -sa-tns- hit **-crv-ic-fv-** mother stump
 ‘The child has made the mother to be hit by the stump.’

Just like the adversative reading, in the accidental interpretation, the causee is interpreted as affected to negative results. However, unlike the adversative reading, the negative results in accidental semantics neither foreseen nor intended. (20) can therefore, be understood in the context that may be the child was running away and the mother chasing after her, when she fell on the root stump. The tripping and falling of the mother on the root stump was not anticipated, intended or foreseen, not by the mother or the child. Consider another example (21);

- (21) Kirimi -a-ku- ring **-ith-i-** a Mugendi ibiga
 Kirimi -sa-tns- hit **-crv-ic-fv-** Mugendi stone
 ‘Kirimi made Mugendi to be hit by a stone.’

It could be interpreted to mean that the stone was not aimed at Mugendi but at Kirimi. Someone was aiming Kirimi with a stone but on Kirimi dodging, it missed him and landed on Mugendi instead. This way the results are purely accidental in that as Kirimi dodges, he does not do it so that the stone hits Mugendi. In this context, the event has to hold, as one cannot, for instance in (21) say that Kirimi made Mugendi to be hit by a stone but it did not. Table 2 contains some verbs that show accidental reading when the causative morpheme **-ith-** embeds a subject.

Table 2. Sample Verbs Showing Accidental Reading in Gichuka -ith-

Plain	Causative	Gloss
tink-a (bump)	tink- ith-i-a	(cause to be knocked)
ring-a (hit)	ring- ith-i-a	(cause to be hit)
kiny-a (step on)	kiny- ith-i-a	(cause to be stepped on)

munt-a (prick)	munt- ith -i-a (cause to be pricked)
kor-a (choke)	kor- ith -i-a (cause to be choked)
bari-a (scratch)	bar- ith -i-a (cause to be scratched)

In all the causatives in table 2, it is noted that the caused events are purely accidental and not anticipated, unlike in other readings where the results are always deliberately intended or expected from the actions of either the causer or the causee.

(f) Idiomatic Semantics

Having established that the two are distinct, one important distinction is that while *-i-* may involve non-coercive causation, *-ith-* entails coercion. In certain contexts, however, stative verbs may resemble causative morphemes but do not necessarily have a causative meaning. Consider (22) with *-ith-*

- (22) *Riu Kagendo a-gu-ku-ith-i-a- meecuwe montbe*
 now Kagendo -sa-tns die crc ic fv sa-grandparents hers all
 Kagendo has now lost all her grandparents (through death)

Furthermore in Gĩchuka the causative *-i-* was seen to lexicalize to form idioms. Consider (23 and (24)

- (23a) *ũk-a*
 come -fv-
 come

- (b) *ũk-i-a-*
 wake/erect -ic- fv-

X wakes Y up

Y gets an erection

- (24a) *Rĩm-a*
 cultivate -fv-

weed

- (b) *rĩm-i-a*
 cultivate -ic-fv-
 X works for a wage

From the face value, the *-ith-* and *-i-* in 22, 23 and 24 are no different from the morphemes *-ith-* and *-i-* used for causation. This applies to the morphemes in (22b), however, the semantics are not those of causation. While (22) has the semantics of a stative, (23b and 24b) have idiomatic reading. In fact, Leipzig Rule presents challenges in the glossing of idioms since the words cannot be inferred.

Having discussed the various readings, we now summarize their contexts in a table format showing their nature in terms of directness or indirectness and the likelihood of the causative event occurring or not. It should be noted, however, that though idiomatic semantics is classified as causatives, it is on the basis of identical semblance and not causation par se. Table 3 shows the properties of all causative contexts

Synergy between Levels

One would wonder why adjective would be categorized as one broad class of verbs. The explanation given (at least in this study) was the observed behavior of adjectives to exhibit verbal characteristics under causation. Besides suffixation on verbs, *-i-* can attach to other items like adjectives and nouns making them verbs of becoming. This means that besides being a transitivity marker, it is also a de-adjectivizer, verbalizer and a denominal if attached on nouns. Consider example (25).

(25a) irinda -ni-ri-eru

Dress -f-sa- white

‘The dress is white.’

(b) Karimi -a-ku-eru -b-i-a- irinda

Karimi -sa-tns- white verbalizer -ic-fv- dress

Karimi has whitened the dress (by use of blue/bleach)

From examples (25), the adjectives *-eru-* (white) has been de-adjectivized through verbalization of the final consonant into *eru-b-i-a* (whiten) as indicated by /**b**/ before the causative *-i-*. The prompt is a phonological process consonant insertion, hence, a voiceless bilabial /β/, which becomes part of the root and the resultant, is a verbal complex. In the operation, the short causative suffix *-i-* becomes the verbalizer prompting the insertion of /β/.

According to Distributed Morphology (DM), (Halle and Marantz, 1993), morphology is not concentrated in a single component of grammar but is distributed among several other components. In fact, this notion is also shared by Baker (1988) in his Mirror Principle, which states, “Morphological operations reflect (mirror) syntactic operations.” According to them, different components of grammar interact at different levels to bring about vocabulary items which are finally used at the spell-out stage. These levels are; Deep Structure (D-S) Syntactic Structure (SS) Morphological Structure (MS) Phonological Form (PF) and Logical Form (LF). A morpho-syntactic feature for instance [cause] in our case are produced, manipulated and operated on by different mechanisms within these levels before they are realized as vocabulary items for spell-out. For instance, the morpho-syntactic features are produced at syntactic component by such processes as head movement and word formation rules (syntax), manipulated by syntactic operations like move and merge still at the syntactic level and further operated on by morphological operations at the morphological level (morphology) to bring about their phonological forms at the phonological level (phonology), at which stage they undergo operations such as re-adjustment and phonological rules before they are finally spelled-out as vocabulary items.

Causation is an event realized by someone or something else called the cause outside the one ordering the event called the causer. Affixed on the verb or adjective, the resultant is a single morphological complex with varying semantics such as coercion, assistance, trickery, adversative

and accidental. Largely, though referred to as causative morphemes, -ith-, -i- have been seen to produce other semantics such as idioms through lexicalization. That said, there is huge evidence of an interrelationship between the grammatical levels in the production, manipulation, and insertion of causative morphemes from syntactic feature {cause} to morphological -ith-i- to phonological strings /ið-i/.

Conclusion

A lot of details especially in morphology have been missing in under researched languages such as Gichuka. This paper makes two significant contributions with regard to the same, an area considered central to the study of any language. Firstly, there is a detailed description of the morphological causatives and the semantics conveyed in their usage and secondly is the contribution of the components as a result of their interplay. This work can pied-pipe a further investigation into what circumstances render the varied interpretations of the morphological causatives and evaluate whether suffix -i- fits the description 'causative'. The assumption, however is that there were more instances of application of idiomatization than were found here.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest

References

- Baker, M. (1988). *Incorporation: A theory of grammatical function changing*. University of Chicago Press.
- Carlsson, M., Dahl, G. B., & Rooth, D.-O. (2015). The effect of schooling on cognitive skills. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 97(3), 533–547. https://doi.org/10.1162/REST_a_00501
- Chomsky, N. (1988). *Language and problems of knowledge*. MIT Press.
- Christian, L. (1982). Directions for interlinear morphemic translations. *Folia Linguistica*, 16(1–4), 199–224. <https://doi.org/10.1515/flin.1982.16.1-4.199>
- Gentles, S. J., Charles, C., Ploeg, J., & McKibbin, K. A. (2015). Sampling in qualitative research: Insights from an overview of the methods literature. *The Qualitative Report*, 20(11), 1772–1789. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2015.2373>
- Good, J. (2005). Reconstructing morpheme order in Bantu: The case of causativization and applicativization. *Diachronica*, 22(1), 3–57. <https://doi.org/10.1075/dia.22.1.03goo>
- Halle, M., & Marantz, A. (1993). Distributed morphology and the pieces of inflection. In K. Hale & S. J. Keyser (Eds.), *The view from Building 20: Essays in linguistics in honor of Sylvain Bromberger* (pp. 111–176). MIT Press.
- Kenya National Bureau of Statistics. (2020). *2019 Kenya population and housing census: Volume I: Population by county and sub-county*. Government Printer.
- Kombo, D. K., & Tromp, D. L. A. (2006). *Proposal and thesis writing: An introduction*. Paulines Publications Africa.
- McCombes, S. (2019). Dislocating identity: Desegregation and the transformation of place. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 64, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.05.007>

- McNabb, D. E. (2004). *Research methods for political science: Quantitative and qualitative methods*. M. E. Sharpe.
- Mbaka, N. K., & Kirigia, E. K. (2023). Morpho-syntactic decomposition of place names in proximate sister languages: Gichuka, Gikuyu, Kimenti and Kiambu. *Journal of Languages and Linguistics*, 2(1), 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.51317/jll.v2i1.409>
- Mugenda, A. G., & Mugenda, O. M. (1999). *Research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches*. ACTS Press.
- Muriungi, P. K. (2010). Accounting for the readings of the causative morpheme in Kiitharaka. *Nordic Journal of African Studies*, 19(3), 180–199.
- Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Robert, A. (2008). Role and manifestation of causative morpheme ‘chi’ in Cuzco Quechua [Master’s thesis, University of Pittsburgh].
- Swadesh, M. (1955). Towards greater accuracy in lexicostatistic dating. *International Journal of American Linguistics*, 21(2), 121–137. <https://doi.org/10.1086/464321>
- White, G. C. (2001). The effects of class, age, gender, and race on musical preferences: An examination of the omnivore/univore framework [Master’s thesis, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University].

